

Advanced Control of a Multilevel Cascaded H-Bridge Converter for PV Applications

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Abstract—The integration of renewable energy systems and specifically of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems into the grid has become an important issue in the last decade because of the huge expansion of new power plants. PV systems have experienced an important evolution in the overall efficiency and in the variety of locations from low power installations (PV roof systems in domestic and residential applications) to high-power power plants currently reaching up to 550 MW. This fact has led to the appearance of new PV converter topologies and, among them, multilevel converters are very attractive due to its good features such as high nominal power and high quality of output waveforms. In this paper, a multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter is used to directly integrate the PV arrays into the grid. The proposed controller implements independent MPPT algorithms for each H-bridge extracting all the possible power from the available irradiation. Simulation results are presented to demonstrate the good performance of the PV system. The proposed system is modular and can be easily scaled to reach higher power so it could be used in large PV plants just adding extra H-bridges to the converter.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of renewable energy systems into the grid has become an important issue in the last decade because of the huge expansion of new power plants based mainly on wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) energy [1], [2]. Although PV systems follow wind energy systems in importance, an important evolution in the total nominal installed power has occurred in the last years. The global total installed power of solar PV was around 136 GW at the end of 2013, to be compared with just 1.5 GW in 2000 [3].

Over the past five years (2008-2013), solar PV has averaged an annual growth rate of over 40% (for instance, from 102 to 136GW during 2013) but PV generates today a few percent of total yearly electricity production. Germany is the leader of this energy sector in 2013 accounting for around 26% of the global PV market with 35.5 GW installed followed by China (18.3 GW), Italy (17.6 GW), Japan (13.6 GW), US (12 GW) and Spain (5.6 GW). In 2013 the growth has been mostly concentrated in a few countries like China (11.3 GW), Japan (6.9 GW), US (4.8 GW) and Germany (3.3 GW) [4].

Grid-connected PV installations represent 99% of the global total installed power and they cover from low power installations (PV roof systems in domestic and residential applications) to high power power plants currently reaching up to 550 MW (Topaz Solar Farm Project in USA to be operating

during 2015). This fact has led to the appearance of new PV converter topologies and, among them, multilevel converters are very attractive due to its good features such as high nominal power and high quality of output waveforms [5]–[12]. In this way, the focus of the researchers has been attracted and PV systems using neutral-point-clamped converters [13], cascaded H-bridge converters [14]–[17] or other hybrid multilevel converters [18]–[22] have been recently addressed. In this paper, a multilevel H-bridge cascaded converter is used to directly integrate the PV arrays into the grid.

II. PV SYSTEM STRUCTURE

The structure of the proposed PV system is formed by the connection of different PV arrays to the grid via a multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter with three H-bridges (also named power cells) as represented in Fig. 1. Each PV array is directly connected to the dc-link of each H-bridge of the power converter without using any power interface such as a dc/dc converter. The galvanic isolation (if required) could be achieved by using a low frequency transformer to connect the converter to the grid. The PV system structure can be easily extended just by using a higher number of H-bridges in order to increase the nominal power of the power plant. The corresponding controller could be defined following the concepts introduced in this work.

III. PROPOSED CONTROLLER AND MODULATION STRATEGIES

The proposed control and modulation algorithms have two objectives:

- Generate the desired output voltage v_{an}^* obtained by the external controller.
- Control the dc voltage of each H-bridge of the multilevel cascaded converter (V_{dci} , $i=1, \dots, 3$) in order to implement the MPPT controller achieving the maximum power operation.

A. First Stage Controller for the Entire PV system

The first stage control strategy implemented in the PV system is represented in Fig. 2. It is based on two control loops. The external control loop is devoted to control the total dc voltage of the dc side of the multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter. So, this controller is focused on regulating

Fig. 1. Structure of the proposed grid-connected PV system formed by PV arrays connected to a three-cell cascaded multilevel converter

Fig. 2. Structure of the first stage controller for the entire PV system

the sum of the power cell dc voltages to its desired value. This controller does not consider the individual control of the dc voltage of each power cell. The inner strategy to control each dc voltage will be introduced in subsection III-B.

The output of this control loop is the power to be drawn from or to the grid which is calculated depending on the sum of the instantaneous quadratic dc voltage errors of the power cells dc voltages. This reference power (output of the external loop) is used to calculate the reference current through the grid connection inductor and the internal control loop uses it to finally obtain the desired phase voltage to be generated by the converter (v_{an}^*).

B. Proposed Strategy to Control the Individual DC Voltages

In the proposed PV system, a second stage controller is implemented where individual MPPT controllers determine, each sampling time, the desired dc voltage of each PV array V_{dci}^* ($i = 1, \dots, 3$) to obtain the maximum power from the sun irradiance. In the three-cell cascaded H-bridge converter, three independent conventional perturb and observe MPPT algorithms have been implemented to determine V_{dci}^* ($i = 1, \dots, 3$). However, in the proposed external controller for the entire PV system introduced in the previous section, there is not any mechanism to assure that each dc voltage tends to its desired value V_{dci}^* ($i = 1, \dots, 3$). This issue is addressed in this section. All the process to determine the final voltage \vec{V}_m to be used by the modulator is summarized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Scheme of the second stage controller to control the power cell dc voltages.

The proposed controller is based on the multidimensional modulation technique introduced in [23]. As a three-cell cascaded H-bridge converter is considered, it has to be always fulfilled that the phase voltage v_{an} is the sum of the power cell output voltages. So, the desired phase voltage v_{an}^* also has to meet this requirement, fulfilling that

$$v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = v_{an}^*. \quad (1)$$

where v_i ($i = 1, \dots, 3$) are the voltages averaged over a sampling period by power cell i .

This equation represents all the possible output voltages of the power cells which can generate an specific value of the phase voltage v_{an}^* . In fact, this equation represents a plane (plane Π) as represented in Fig. 4. Among all the possible solutions, as a starting point, the proposed strategy considers that all the power cells generate the same voltage averaged over a sampling period determining the components v_{eqi} as

$$v_{eqi} = \frac{v_{an}^*}{3}, i = 1, \dots, 3. \quad (2)$$

This is the solution if a conventional phase-shifted PWM modulation method is applied to a multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter. In this way, all the H-bridges generate the same voltage (with the corresponding phase shifting) leading to a natural power equalization and minimum distortion. However, this conventional solution has to be modified if it is required to control the dc voltage imbalance of each power cell.

The proposed method takes into account the instantaneous quadratic dc voltage error Δ_i defined as

$$\Delta_i = (V_{dci}^*)^2 - (V_{dci})^2, i = 1, \dots, 3. \quad (3)$$

The instantaneous quadratic dc voltage error Δ_i shows how the voltage component v_i should be modified in order to reduce the dc voltage imbalance if the phase current i_a is negative. Each component v_{ci} is ideally the voltage to be generated by power cell i to control its dc voltage V_{dci} and can be determined as

$$\vec{V}_c = (v_{c1}, v_{c2}, v_{c3}), \quad (4)$$

$$v_{ci} = v_{eqi} + \Delta_i, i = 1, \dots, 3. \quad (5)$$

However, in general, vector \vec{V}_c does not belong to plane Π and therefore cannot be a solution to be used by the modulator to generate v_{an}^* . The final vector to be used in the modulation stage can be calculated as the projection of vector \vec{V}_c on plane Π . This new vector \vec{V}_m can be determined as follows where

Fig. 4. Vectorial representation of the proposed modulation method for a three-cell H-bridge cascaded converter.

Fig. 5. VI curve and PV curve of each PV array

a proportional controller k_p has been added to tune up the voltage imbalance control effect on the final voltages to be generated:

$$\vec{V}_m = (v_{m1}, v_{m2}, v_{m3}), \quad (6)$$

$$v_{mi} = v_{eqi} - \text{sign}(i_a)k_p(\Delta_i - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 \Delta_i), i = 1, \dots, 3. \quad (7)$$

All the process addressed in this subsection is summarized in Fig. 3. In this calculation, it is taken into account that the effect on the dc voltages depends on the direction of the phase current. This is done introducing factor $\text{sign}(i_a)$ multiplying the dc voltage imbalance part in expression (7).

Finally, the voltage \vec{V}_m is applied to a conventional phase-shifted PWM. Each component v_{mi} is used as input of a unipolar PWM modulator with 60° of phase shifting between consecutive H-bridges (180° divided by the number of H-bridges of the converter). This fact leads to advantages such as the multiplicative effect of the effective switching frequency in the output waveforms, i.e., the effective switching frequency of the output phase voltage v_{an} and the phase current i_a is higher than the switching frequency of each H-bridge. On the other hand, phase-shifted PWM achieves a natural power equalization under quasi-equal irradiance conditions. Under very different irradiance conditions in each H-bridge, the proposed controller slightly moves the power drawn by each H-bridge to achieve the MPPT operation point.

Fig. 6. Results of the proposed modulation and control strategies under several transient and steady state conditions. From up to bottom: Phase voltage v_{an} , Phase current i_a , dc voltages of each power cell V_{dci} ($i = 1, \dots, 3$) and instantaneous power drawn by the converter.

Fig. 7. Results of the proposed modulation and control strategies with equal irradiance in each power cell ($1kW/m^2$). From up to bottom: Phase voltage v_{an} , Phase current i_a and dc voltages of each power cell V_{dci} ($i = 1, \dots, 3$).

IV. RESULTS

The proposed control method has been tested and some simulation results are shown in this section. The model has been implemented using Matlab-Simulink with SimpowerSystems toolbox. The carriers frequency has been fixed to 2 kHz, the inductor is equal to 1 mH and the dc-link capacitors are 6.6 mF. The PV arrays irradiance λ_i ($i=1, \dots, 3$) is variable. Each PV array is built using Kyocera KD135GX-LP modules with 10 series modules and 2 parallel strings and the characteristic curves are plotted in Fig. 5.

The sun irradiance has been initially fixed to $1 kW/m^2$ for all the PV arrays. The MPPT controllers determine the desired dc voltage values to V_{dci}^* which are equal to 177 volts according the characteristics of the PV arrays implemented in the model (see Fig. 5). This optimal operation point is achieved by the proposed controller as can be observed in Fig. 6 and more in detail in Fig. 7. The obtained output phase voltage v_{an} and phase current i_a have low distortion and the dc voltages are controlled with the presence of a unavoidable 100 Hz ripple around eight volts peak to peak causing a 100 Hz ripple in the power drawn into the grid around 600 watts peak to peak.

At simulation time equal to 1 second, the irradiance of cell 1 is reduced to $0.6 kW/m^2$ and the corresponding MPPT controller determines that the optimum dc voltage of cell 1 V_{dc1}^* is 173 volts while $V_{dc2}^* = V_{dc3}^* = 177$ volts. It can be observed in Fig. 6 that the MPPT is successfully achieved after 0.3 seconds. A detail of this operation point is represented in Fig. 8 showing the results in steady state.

At simulation time equal to 1.5 seconds, the irradiance of cell 2 is also reduced to $0.75 kW/m^2$ and the corresponding MPPT controller determines that the optimum dc voltage of cell 2 V_{dc2}^* is 175 volts while $V_{dc1}^* = 173$ volts and $V_{dc3}^* = 177$ volts. It can be observed in Fig. 6 that the MPPT is again achieved after 0.3 seconds. A detail of this operation point is represented in Fig. 9 showing the results in steady state.

V. CONCLUSIONS

PV systems are being installed all over the world covering from low power to high power applications becoming one of the most important renewable energy sources nowadays. The

Fig. 8. Results of the proposed modulation and control strategies with an irradiance change from $\lambda_1=\lambda_2=\lambda_3=1kW/m^2$ to $\lambda_1=1kW/m^2$, $\lambda_2=0.6kW/m^2$ and $\lambda_3=1kW/m^2$. From up to bottom: Phase voltage v_{an} , Phase current i_a and dc voltages of each power cell V_{dci} ($i = 1, \dots, 3$).

Fig. 9. Results of the proposed modulation and control strategies with an irradiance change from $\lambda_1=1kW/m^2$, $\lambda_2=0.6kW/m^2$ and $\lambda_3=1kW/m^2$ to $\lambda_1=0.75kW/m^2$, $\lambda_2=0.6kW/m^2$ and $\lambda_3=1kW/m^2$. From up to bottom: Phase voltage v_{an} , Phase current i_a and dc voltages of each power cell V_{dci} ($i = 1, \dots, 3$).

use of multilevel converters for PV applications has been studied by the academia and recently some industrial products have appeared in the PV market. Among the multilevel converters, multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter is proposed in this work to be used as the PV inverter of a multistring PV system directly connecting the PV arrays to the grid without using any auxiliary dc/dc converter. Individual MPPT controllers are implemented in each H-bridge of the converter. The proposed control and modulation strategies achieve the MPPT extracting the maximum power from the sun with high performance. The proposed control scheme is based on two stage controllers. The first stage controller achieves the control of the sum of the dc voltages of the H-bridges and the second stage controller controls the dc voltage of each H-bridge to its desired value.

The simplicity of the control method introduced in this paper is very high only including simple mathematical calculations. Therefore, the computational burden is very reduced. The final modulation strategy is a conventional phase-shifted PWM leading to advantages such as the multiplicative effect of the effective switching frequency in the output waveforms and the natural power equalization under quasi-equal irradiance conditions.

The proposed control has been presented for a multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter with three H-bridges but, due

to the modularity of the power converter and the proposed controller, it can be easily extended to be used in a multilevel cascaded H-bridge converter with a higher number of power cells. In this way, the proposed method is suitable to be implemented to integrate into the grid all kind of applications from domestic (less than 3 kW) to PV power plants (hundreds of megawatts).

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